

the allylamino-group is attached to the ring by means of a single bond and hence no hydrolysis.

In conclusion I wish to express my thanks to Dr. P. K. Bose for his advice during the course of the investigation.

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Reactivity of Carbonyl Group in γ -Pyrones and in γ -Pyridones.

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The structure of γ -pyrones (I) and that of γ -pyridones (II) are not in agreement with the fact that in general these compounds do not form an oxime or a phenylhydrazone.

(I)

(II)

We, however, find that by using the more reactive *p*-nitrophenylhydrazine in place of phenylhydrazine, chelidonic ester (I, R = CO₂Et) gives its nitrophenylhydrazone which on hydrolysis gives back chelidonic ester. This reaction of a true ketone justifies the structure (I) for this pyrone. 3:5-Dibromochelidonic ester similarly gives its nitrophenylhydrazone.

When xanthochelidonic ester (acetone dioxalic ester III, R = CO₂Et) is, however, treated with the same reagent two products are obtained of the composition C₁₇H₁₇O₇N₃ (m. p. 146°) and C₂₃H₂₂O₈N₆ (m.p. 210°). The former is isomeric with the nitrophenylhydrazone of chelidonic ester and is regarded as (IV) formed by the action of nitrophenylhydrazine on the dienolic form (III) of acetone dioxalic ester. The compound (m.p. 210°), which can also be prepared by the interaction of nitrophenylhydrazine and (IV) is obviously its nitrophenylhydrazone (V).

This reaction was extended to other triketones of the type of acetone dioxalic ester. Thus diacetylacetone and nitrophenylhydrazine are found to react in molecular proportion to give a product of the composition C₁₃H₁₃O₃N₃. This could not be the nitrophenylhydrazone of dimethyl pyrone, as dimethylpyrone itself does not form a nitrophenylhydrazone. The compound must, therefore, be a pyridone, formed as in the case of acetone dioxalic ester. Moreover, as it forms a nitrophenylhydrazone C₁₉H₁₈O₄N₆ the pyridone must be a true ketone. The structures of diacetylacetone, of the pyridone and of its nitrophenylhydrazone are (III), (IV) and (V) (R = Me).

Somewhat similar results have been obtained from dipropionylacetone by Deshapande, Dingankar and Kokil (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 595).

Although nitrophenylhydrazine has no action on dimethyl-, diethyl-, or dipropylpyrone, it reacts energetically upon pyrone itself

(I, R=H) giving a product $C_{17}H_{14}O_4N_6$, in the formation of which two molecules of the reagent have reacted. By decreasing the proportion of the reagent no other product could be isolated. As the two oxygen atoms in the pyrone are the only points of attack by the reagent the compound must have the structure V (R=H). It is a base and forms a chloroplatinate. On dry distillation with caustic potash a few drops of a strongly basic liquid soluble in water and having odour of pyridine were obtained, but the quantity was too small for further investigation.

Chelidonic acid (I, R=CO₂H) and comanic ester (I, R=H; R=CO₂Et) similarly react with two molecules of nitrophenylhydrazine yielding corresponding products of structure (V). In no case could any definite product of the reaction of one molecule of nitrophenylhydrazine be isolated.

The nitrophenylhydrazones of *N*-substituted pyridones (V) must have been formed from the corresponding pyrones (I) *via* either (a) the *N*-substituted pyridones (IV), or (b) the nitrophenylhydrazones of the pyrones. The latter route seems to be unlikely because nitrophenylhydrazone of chelidonic ester does not react with nitrophenylhydrazine. In the former route attempts to get the *N*-substituted pyridones (IV) have been unsuccessful. This is probably due to the fact that the rate of phenylhydrazone formation of such *N*-substituted pyridones as have been actually isolated (IV, R=CO₂Et or Me) is quite rapid (less than 10 minutes for completion of the reaction), as compared to the rate of their own formation. Indeed in the formation of (IV) from (III) using 1 molecule of nitrophenylhydrazine some quantity of (V) is invariably produced although the reaction is allowed to go only for a short time.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Nitrophenylhydrazone of chelidonic ester.—The pyrone and the reagent in molecular proportions were heated together in absolute alcoholic solution for half an hour. On removing excess of the solvent and rubbing, the phenylhydrazone separated as a reddish yellow mass. It crystallises from alcohol in golden yellow needles and from benzene in scarlet needles, m. p. 216°. (Found: C, 54.0; H, 4.2; N, 11.8. $C_{17}H_{17}O_7N_3$ requires C, 54.4; H, 4.5; N, 11.2 per cent).

Hydrolysis of the phenylhydrazone.—The compound was refluxed in glacial acetic acid solution in a current of dry hydrochloric acid

for 1 hour. On cooling and pouring in water the unchanged phenylhydrazone precipitated which was filtered off. On making the filtrate feebly alkaline, an oil separated which gradually solidified and on crystallisation from petroleum melted at 63° and was identified as chelidonic ester by mixed melting point.

The nitrophenylhydrazone of dibromochelidonic ester, which was prepared as above, crystallises from alcohol in needles, m. p. 120° . (Found: Br, 30.9. $C_{17}H_{15}O_7N_2Br_2$ requires Br, 30.0 per cent).

Action of nitrophenylhydrazine on acetonedioxalic ester.—When equimolecular proportions of the two substances react for a short time in boiling absolute alcohol the pyridone (IV, $R=CO_2Et$) is the main product formed together with some amount of its nitrophenylhydrazone (V, $R=CO_2Et$). The longer the duration of heating, the greater becomes the yield of (V) and in one hour the whole reaction product consists practically of (V). The products are separated by means of alcohol in which (V) is less soluble than (IV). If the reaction is carried out in glacial acetic acid, the pyridone (IV) is more conveniently obtained. The pyridone crystallises from alcohol and melts at 146° . (Found: C, 54.2; H, 4.8; N, 10.9. $C_{17}H_{17}O_7N_3$ requires C, 54.4; H, 4.5; N, 11.2 per cent).

The nitrophenylhydrazone of the pyridone crystallised from acetic acid and melted at 210° . (Found: C, 53.6; H, 4.5; N, 16.7. $C_{23}H_{22}O_8N_6$ requires C, 54.1; H, 4.3; N, 16.4 per cent).

Action of nitrophenylhydrazine on diacetylacetone.—On refluxing in absolute alcohol for 10 minutes molecular proportions of diacetylacetone and nitrophenylhydrazine, the pyridone (IV, $R=Me$) separated on cooling as a pale yellow solid. It crystallised from alcohol in starshaped clusters, m. p. 136° . (Found: C, 60.3; H, 5.3; N, 15.8. $C_{13}H_{13}O_3N_3$ requires C, 60.0; H, 4.8; N, 16.2 per cent).

The nitrophenylhydrazone of the above pyridone (V, $R=Me$) was obtained from the pyridone in glacial acetic acid. It was, however, more conveniently prepared by heating for 10 minutes on a water-bath diacetylacetone (1 mol.) and nitrophenylhydrazine (2 mols.) dissolved in glacial acetic acid. Crystallised from acetic acid it melts at 215° . (Found: C, 58.1; H, 4.3; N, 20.8. $C_{19}H_{18}O_4N_6$ requires C, 57.8; H, 4.6; N, 21.3 per cent).

Action of nitrophenylhydrazine on pyrone.—When pyrone (1 mol.) and nitrophenylhydrazine (2 mols.) were warmed on a water-bath in glacial acetic acid for 5 minutes the nitrophenylhydrazone of pyridone (V, $R=H$) was formed as a yellow solid. After crystallising from

pyridine it melts at 242°. (Found: C, 55.7; H, 4.1; N, 22.6. $C_{17}H_{14}O_4N_6$ requires C, 55.7; H, 3.6; N, 22.9 per cent).

Action of nitrophenylhydrazine on chelidonic acid.—This was carried out as in the case of pyrone, but dilute acetic acid was used owing to chelidonic acid being sparingly soluble in glacial acetic acid. The nitrophenylhydrazone of pyridone (V, R=CO₂H) crystallised from methyl alcohol as yellow needles, m. p. 210°. (Found: C, 49.8; H, 3.3; N, 18.4. $C_{19}H_{14}O_8N_6$ requires C, 50.0; H, 3.1; N, 18.5 per cent).

Action of nitrophenylhydrazine on comanic ester.—This was carried out as in the last two cases substituting alcohol in place of acetic acid. The nitrophenylhydrazone of pyridone (V, R=H; R=CO₂Et) crystallised from acetic acid in yellow prisms, m. p. 220°. (Found: C, 54.8; H, 4.0; N, 19.4. $C_{20}H_{18}O_6N_6$ requires C, 54.8; H, 4.1; N, 19.2 per cent).

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